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**CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS ON WAYS TO IMPROVE
CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN CREATIVITY
SCHOOLS THROUGH ENGLISH LESSONS**

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Abstract: This article presents conclusions and recommendations on improving the critical thinking skills of high school students in creativity schools through English lessons. The study emphasizes the importance of critical thinking in the educational process, particularly in fostering intellectual and creative capacities. Various methods and approaches are suggested, including project-based learning, debates, simulations, and critical reading techniques, which can effectively cultivate critical thinking abilities. The article outlines the pedagogical and psychological foundations for enhancing critical thinking and provides a framework for integrating these skills into English lessons. Recommendations focus on developing tailored teaching strategies, teacher training, and incorporating critical thinking elements into assessment systems to encourage students to think analytically and independently.

Keywords: critical thinking, high school students, creativity schools, English lessons, project-based learning, debates, simulations, critical reading, teaching strategies, teacher training, assessment systems.

**ВЫВОДЫ И РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ПО СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЮ НАВЫКОВ
КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ СТАРШЕКЛАССНИКОВ В ТВОРЧЕСКИХ
ШКОЛАХ С ПОМОЩЬЮ УРОКОВ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА**

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлены выводы и рекомендации по совершенствованию навыков критического мышления старшеклассников в творческих школах с помощью уроков английского языка. В исследовании подчеркивается важность критического мышления в образовательном процессе, особенно в развитии интеллектуальных и творческих способностей. Предлагаются различные методы и подходы, включая проектное обучение, дебаты, моделирование и методы критического чтения, которые могут эффективно развивать способности к критическому мышлению. В статье излагаются педагогические и психологические основы развития критического мышления и предлагаются основы для интеграции этих навыков на уроках английского языка. Рекомендации направлены на разработку индивидуальных стратегий преподавания, подготовку учителей и включение элементов критического мышления в системы оценивания, чтобы побудить учащихся мыслить аналитически и независимо.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, старшеклассники, творческие школы, уроки английского языка, проектное обучение, дебаты, симуляции, критическое чтение, стратегии преподавания, подготовка учителей, системы оценивания.

INTRODUCTION

In the world, the research areas of modern pedagogy are changing, the need for improving the system of developing critical thinking skills, namely creativity, the ability to analyze data, the ability to draw reasonable conclusions from the learned information, perseverance, the ability to make decisions. The 21st century is the era of technology and the Internet, and the large-scale dissemination of information has become an integral part of modern society. In this period, the need for any person to have the skills to analyze the information received, to assess its reliability and truthfulness is increasing. The development of universal competence through the formation of such skills is becoming important. Because this is an important factor in ensuring the effective and responsible participation of a person in society. Especially in the process of training future personnel, not only the formation of professional skills, but also the development of intellectual skills such as “thinking out of the box” (deep and creative thinking), which requires a comprehensive and new approach, is one of the urgent issues.

Globally, the development of critical thinking skills is considered an important factor in improving the worldview, level of knowledge and other skills of young students. Therefore, a lot of scientific research is being conducted in this field. Critical thinking not only deepens the process of learning, but also helps to develop analytical and creative abilities of students. With these skills, students develop the ability to think independently and logically to solve complex problems, analyze evidence, and make informed decisions. Especially in English classes, a lot of attention is paid to the development of critical thinking, because the process of learning a foreign language requires students to accept, evaluate and adapt to different cultures and perspectives. Critical thinking is important in this process because it helps students develop their own perspective, analyze different cultural contexts, and apply the knowledge learned in different situations.

Improving the system of teaching foreign languages in New Uzbekistan, developing linguistic competence as well as life skills, creativity, communication skills, team work ability, perseverance of the students who are the future of New Uzbekistan, creation of a system aimed at developing critical thinking skills, gradually adapting national qualification requirements in this direction to international analogues is one of the urgent tasks before us¹. For this purpose, at a time when the structure of the new educational programs created in school education is being developed in accordance with world standards, it will be necessary to introduce specific mechanisms that provide for the development of students’ critical thinking skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The introduction of new technologies in education is becoming more widespread and has a positive effect on the quality of the educational experience. Teachers should constantly look for new methods and approaches to education and use innovative pedagogical technologies in their work to improve learning results. Methods and methods of creating a system of developing vital and adaptive skills of students in the continuous education system, forming and developing critical thinking skills by introducing innovative educational technologies in the modernized education process of New Uzbekistan D. Sharipova, K. Riskulova, M. Yakubbayev, N.A. Mamadjonova, O. Dadabolayeva, O. Musurmonova, R. Juraev, T. Nazarov, Kh. Mamatkulov, Sh.A. Abdullayeva, Sh. Sharipov’s critical thinking, its characteristics and general description, conducted scientific research.

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" // <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

A.I. Lipkina, B.M. scientists from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States. Teplov, D.M.Shakirova, Fatih Uzturk, L.V.Khokhlova, M.V.Klarin, V.I.Mushtavinskaya, Yu.A.Samarin and others have researched the pedagogical and psychological foundations of improving students' critical thinking skills during foreign language teaching.

Foreign D. Halpern, E. Torrance, J.P. Guilford, H. Puchta, M. Fahim, M. Scriven, R.H. Enis, R. Paul, R. Boostrom, and Özkaya, Ö. Miraç; In the studies of scientists like S.Nuriye, the importance of critical thinking in the educational process has been revealed at various levels and the theoretical foundations of the concept of critical thinking have been studied.

The issues of development of students' critical thinking skills have been studied in scientific works, but the problems related to the methodology and technologies of development of critical thinking skills in English language education of creativity schools students have not been sufficiently researched.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article uses a methodology of comparative analysis with the aim of studying how much material is provided and their importance in education, aimed at the development of critical thinking skills in schools of general education and creativity. Content analysis, textbook assessment and content analysis based on expert conclusions are carried out in the research process. The study uses a method of studying the comparative situation, evaluating the content aspects of them aimed at developing critical thinking through the analysis of samples of textbooks of creative and secondary schools.

General and creative schools' widely used textbooks were selected for analysis based on a targeted selection strategy. At least five textbooks were selected from each type of school, covering grades 6-12. The selection process focused on textbooks published in the last five years in order to ensure compliance with current teaching practices. Also in foreign literature are studied and examples of thoughts about the importance and process of critical thinking.

The data is revised using qualitative thematic analysis and content frequency analysis. The materials presented for the development of critical thinking skills are identified by similarity and differences, and the results are compared by creative and general education schools.

The results of the study are aimed at identifying opportunities for better integration of critical thinking skills in English textbooks, and in particular, to provide effective recommendations for secondary schools.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Based on the results of a study devoted to the problem of developing critical thinking skills in students in the processes of teaching upper class English, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. In upper-class English classes, the development of critical thinking skills in students is recognized as an important factor in improving the quality of teaching in the process of continuing education, since this process serves to form in students the ability to consciously and analytically treat events and phenomena in the environment, analyze them deeply, make independent decisions and solve problems in innovative ways. Critical thinking also plays an important role in expanding students' creativity and intellectual abilities, as these skills help them to analyze information in a multifaceted way, get out of existing stereotypes and find new approaches. As a result, the development of critical thinking not only strengthens language skills, but also develops students' skills such as logical analysis, global perspective, and creative approach to modern problems, allowing them to grow into competitive, independent-minded, and intellectually developed individuals in the future.

2. In order to improve critical thinking in students of the upper class in English lessons, it is important to deeply perceive the meaning and essence of this process, analyze various approaches and factors in the process of studying problems, and comprehensively study the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the development of critical thinking. In the formation of critical thinking, it is necessary to take into account the psychological factors of the pedagogical process, to develop opportunities for deep and logical analysis on the level of intellectual development of students, the development of independent thinking skills in them, problem situations. Also, the methodological training of teachers of upper class English should be recognized as an important factor determining the success of this process, since the methodological approaches of teachers in teaching critical-analytical thinking play a leading role in the formation of students' abilities to use analytical approaches to solving problems. Thus, in order to develop critical thinking, it is necessary not only to optimize didactic processes, but also to increase the scientific and methodological competencies of educators.

3. The application of exercise technology on platforms based on an improved didactic model of teaching high school students to critical thinking in English classes manifests itself as an effective method that significantly develops students' thinking skills. Such platforms allow students to take a critical-analytical approach, study problems in a complex way and improve their ability to make independent decisions on various issues. The integration of these technologies into the educational process serves to strengthen the interactive and reflective components of the didactic model, which allows students not only to deepen their knowledge of the language being studied, but also to upgrade their creative and critical thinking skills in various areas of knowledge. At the same time, the exercises carried out through the platforms are aimed at developing students' skills to consistently and accurately express thought, be able to substantiate arguments and understand the connection between different thoughts, which has a great influence on their intellectual development in general.

4. In English classes, the organization of activities aimed at developing critical thinking skills in students in a consistent and goal-oriented way plays an important role in the development of students' skills to defend their point of view, analyze arguments, and evaluate various alternative decisions. This activity focuses on the basic components of the critical thinking process – argument reasoning, consideration of alternatives in decision making, and the development of independent thinking, providing a framework for expanding the intellectual capacity of students. The formation of critical thinking skills is directly related to the improvement of the ability to make responsible decisions necessary for success at the stage of higher education and in future professional life. Through this process, students not only strengthen knowledge, but also enrich them with creative and analytical thinking, which greatly contributes to their formation as a competitive, responsible and goal-oriented person.

5. In order to successfully carry out the tasks set before the educational system in the process of developing critical thinking skills in students in upper-class English classes, it is necessary to further improve this activity taking into account the young, psychological and physiological characteristics of students. Individual levels of development and cognitive abilities of students occupy an important place in the process of critical thinking, therefore, educators should organize the educational process on the basis of an individual-oriented approach. In this, the educational methodology is further enriched and the active participation of students is ensured, taking into account the psychological characteristics of students, levels of assimilation and intellectual abilities. The effectiveness of the development of critical thinking is ensured through approaches

aimed at improving the thinking, analysis, independent and creative decision-making abilities of students, which will serve to deeply assimilate modern knowledge in them and develop skills for responsible decision-making in the future.

6. The results of the study scientifically and experimentally justify the fact that critical thinking skills can be effectively developed through the use of debate, simulation and project-based teaching technologies among upperclassmen. These technologies show high efficacy in developing students' problem situation analysis, alternative decision assessment, and evidence reasoning skills. In particular, while debate techniques encourage students to explore different perspectives and logically base their thoughts, simulation technologies enhance students' analytical thinking abilities by modeling real-life States. Project-based teaching, on the other hand, improves students' skills in creative thinking, teamwork, and solving multi-level issues. Studies suggest that the integration of these techniques will increase the effectiveness of students in developing critical thinking, necessitating a more extensive application of these technologies in the pedagogical process.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to ensure the effectiveness of the process of developing critical thinking skills in upper-class English classes, it is necessary to prepare teachers for a methodology that uses technologies that motivate CT: special methodological trainings are held so that teachers know how to help students in this process. They should discuss complex topics, ask analytical questions, and encourage students to provide evidence.

1. The use of project and debate-based educational technologies in upper-class education, particularly in English classes, is recognized as an effective method for shaping critical approaches and developing decision-making skills in students. Project-based education allows students to independently conduct research activities, deeply analyze problem situations and offer creative solutions. Debate techniques, on the other hand, train students to analyze different opinions, draw evidential-based conclusions, and apply CT to the decision-making process. Through the application of these technologies in the educational process, students acquire the intellectual and communicative skills necessary to effectively solve future problems and make responsible decisions, which serve to ensure their success not only in academic, but also in professional life.

2. Analytical reading and the submission of written works are an important pedagogical tool in the development of CT in students. Students are instructed to analyze complex texts, understand their content deeply, analyze different points of view and draw reasonable conclusions, in the process of which their thought processes are teranized by accurately and consistently expressing their thoughts in writing. Through such assignments, students not only develop the skills of understanding and analyzing the text, but also their skills for logical consistency, evidential reasoning and independent reasoning are enhanced. As a result, it is ensured that students are able to strictly and logically justify their point of view in their written work and are ready to make decisions based on scientific approaches.

3. Conducting simulation and role-playing exercises is used as an effective tool for upperclassmen to simulate problem-solving processes by creating real-life situations. This approach allows students to practice their theoretical knowledge, apply creative approaches to solve real-life problems, and develop CT skills. In the simulation process, students express themselves in specific roles, exploring different perspectives on different individuals and situations. This serves to enhance their empathy skills, provide in-depth analysis of problem situations in the decision-making process, and develop skills to act on logical grounds. As a result,

students are prepared for situations they face in real life and acquire the ability to express their thoughts clearly and effectively.

4. Adding elements to the assessment system that involve critical thinking is important in developing CTni skills in the upper class. The inclusion of criteria that take students into account in the process of assessing the skills of independent thinking, analytical approaches and drawing conclusions on the basis of evidence will help to organize the educational process more ineffectively and purposefully. Such an assessment system allows students to independently create their own thoughts, rationalize and test their theories in practice. Evaluation criteria aimed at developing CT allow students to apply their knowledge in a practical context, enhance their analysis and synthesis skills, and participate more actively in the process of mutual exchange of ideas. Thus, the improvement of the assessment system serves to strengthen students' critical thinking skills, improve their academic success, and form independent and responsible decision-making skills in their future professional activities.

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